

1 **The sigmoid colon transcriptome in Campylobacter jejuni enteritis.**

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6 We characterized here for the first time the transcriptome of the sigmoid colon during enteritis resulting
7 from human Campylobacter jejuni infection.

8 Enteritis resulting from Campylobacter jejuni infection was defined by activation of *Reg1a* and the
9 peptidase inhibitor *Pi3*. Cells underwent activation of primary inflammatory responses (e.g., *Lta4h*) with
10 activation of innate immune system (e.g., *Nlrp7*). The sigmoid colon silenced immune receptor *Lrrn2*,
11 surface receptors *Cldn8* but activated *Lypd5* and *Cd74*. Toleragenic responses were marked by *Fpr2*
12 activation. The sigmoid colon expressed *Duoxa2* and *Lyn* during enteritis. We describe silencing of *Padi2*
13 with induction of sensor *Zbp1* in the GI tract during bacterial enteritis.

14 Citations

15 1. Blaser, M.J. and Reller, L.B., 1981. Campylobacter enteritis. *New England Journal of Medicine*,
16 305(24), pp.1444-1452.

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